

Fitting of data: JBW-NP-P-5NM-V2 2021-02-18_10-25-22
 $0.0201 \leq q \text{ (nm}^{-1}\text{)} \leq 23.7$
Active parameters: 1, ranges: 1
Background level: 0.00163 ± 0.00153
(Scaling factor: $9.56e+33 \pm 4.57e+31$)
Timing: 10 repetitions of 33.3 ± 1.34 seconds

Range $1.500e-10$ to $1.500e-07$, vol-weighted
totalValue: $1.048e-03 \pm 1.985e-06$
mean: $5.351e-09 \pm 3.302e-12$
variance: $2.710e-18 \pm 1.711e-20$
skew: $5.574e-01 \pm 1.175e-01$
kurtosis: $3.723e+00 \pm 6.389e-01$

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